

THE NEED AND PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF IMPLEMENTATION OF MODERN ECOLOGICAL EDUCATION.

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Abstract: In this article, theoretical and pedagogical foundations of environmental education and training, modern forms, methods and tools of preparing future chemistry teachers for implementation of environmental education and training are studied.

Key words: professional-pedagogical activity, integrative, corporate, national, historical, technological, competence, chemistry, ecology, biosphere, healthy lifestyle, ecological communication, pedagogical process.

INTRODUCTION.

Today, in the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan and in the development of priority tasks related to education, special attention is paid to the protection of the environment and the improvement of the ecological situation. Many normative legal documents, decrees and orders are being adopted in the society on the formation of ecological stability, careful attitude to the environment and rational use of nature, and special tasks have been defined at each level of management. After all, "it is also an important task to improve the environmental control system, revise the procedure for conducting environmental audits, and revitalize the activities of private auditors. Also, the government's attempt to develop a comprehensive plan of measures to reduce environmental risks and preserve the purity of nature is also considered the result of our country's work aimed at creating environmental stability. In the opinion of the head of our state, "the government should develop a comprehensive program of measures to prevent the impact of industrial development on the environment until 2025... Also, with the involvement of influential international experts, it is necessary to develop a project of the ecological code" shows the opinions and the government's position in this regard.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS.

It is appropriate to review the approaches and scientific conclusions of scientists who have conducted research in these areas in order to illuminate the scientific and pedagogical foundations of modern ecological education.

Environmental education should be formed and developed in the educational system up to higher education. In his research, Yu. Ahmadaliyev commented on the importance of proper organization of extracurricular activities in environmental education in school education. "On the basis of the organization of workshops, students' interest in nature will increase, their attitude towards it will increase, their attitude towards it will be formed consciously, and their interest in other educational subjects will increase," he says. Therefore, if environmental competence is formed and developed in preschool and school education, it is possible to achieve the intended goal and to a certain extent get rid of environmental problems caused by the human factor.

Another scientist, N.Abdullayeva, emphasizes in her scientific research that the question of the role of man in the earth's ecosystem should become a topic of attention of ecologists, philosophers, and cultural scientists in connection with the growing ecological crisis. According to his conclusions, "today the world will be saved by people who deeply understand the laws of nature, who feel that man is a part of nature, and who act on this basis. It is necessary for human activity to be in accordance with a purpose and to develop harmoniously with nature, without spontaneous impact on it. This depends on the level of moral-ecological consciousness and culture, which is formed in every person from childhood and continues until the end of his life." Therefore, the main reason for the origin of the global ecological decline is not only the economic growth and increased consumer potential of humanity, but also the "poverty" of its humanistic attitude to nature. Implementation of the above-mentioned effective measures for environmental protection, elimination of a large-scale environmental threat, necessary conditions for the birth and development of a physically healthy young generation for the population of the republic, and ecologically allows to create a clean living environment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

In the implementation of modern environmental education, the issue of common education is important. It shows two relatively independent processes:

☒ the possibility of a complex and systematic approach to environmental education arises from the need to harmonize different areas of education, to connect alternative directions based on a single goal.

☒ it is necessary to maintain the historical and logical consistency of connections between different forms and levels of environmental education, and to ensure connections between their means and methods. In other words, the common character of these directions is manifested in their relationship to each other. In addition, on the basis of connecting education and training with the interests of nature protection, a commonality emerges, and its features become a necessary condition for the development of environmental responsibility.

The reform of the educational system based on environmental needs has moved universal values, including environmental education, to the center of pedagogical policy. The effective solution of this task requires the generalization of all fields of education based on scientific and philosophical methodological principles. In fact, it is in the process of environmental education that there are opportunities to eliminate the gaps and conflicts of various forms of science and social consciousness in the fields of education. Therefore, education in the field of nature protection should be an integral part of the training of qualified personnel at any level of educational complex, rather than being an event artificially and mechanistically added to general education. Its content may change depending on the social, economic, political conditions, and ecological situation in different countries.

The integration of various levels and directions of environmental education represents the adaptation of the "individual" interests of these fields to universal interests. In this context, it is necessary to note the educational role of other forms of activity: traditions, customs, rituals and other rituals in increasing ecological activity and responsibility. Such socio-practical events acquire a unique ecological content. That is, the complex of social values becomes a factor affecting other structural elements of society, being ecological. In particular, ecological education - with increased responsibility in the relevant direction, remains a means of influencing the internal and external political processes of society. In the

process of forming the principles of ecological activity, the culture of ecological thinking, concepts, conclusions, practical relations, socio-political beliefs, and general outlook of the workers are formed by mastering certain theoretical knowledge. In other words, the educational complex prepares a person for active environmental, social and political activity.

CONCLUSION.

In conclusion, the development of ecological education and training in modern educational conditions, the organization of a pedagogical process aimed at forming a careful attitude to the environment affects the development of environmental knowledge and skills in students. Therefore, it is important to use new approaches aimed at the development of environmental competence, and to use different mechanisms of influence.

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